

Lipase (LPS) Assay Kit

(Colorimetric method)

Cat No. A054-1 Pack:50T/48S

1、 Assay principle:

Emulsion mixed from triglyceride and water appears opacification because of its micelles absorb and scatter incident light. Triglyceride trends to hydrolyze under effect by lipase (LPS), this hydrolysis splits micelles and decreases incident ratio and turbidity, decreasing rate correlates with LPS activity.

2、 Reagent composition and preparation

Reagent 1: Substrate buffer, 60ml×2 bottles, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months, pre-warm to 37°C prior to use.

Reagent 2: Tris buffer, 10ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for 6 months.

Reagent 3: Physiologic saline, 10ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C for short period and frozen at -20°C for long period.

Reagent 4: 10ml×1 bottle, can be stored at 4°C hermetically for 6 months.

Please pre-warm all reagents to room temperature prior to use.

3、 Blood serum (or plasma) LPS activity assay

(1) Operation procedure:

- ① Adjust zero of spectrophotometer at 420nm by 1cm light path glass cuvette and Tris buffer.
- ② Pre-warm substrate buffer to 37°C for more than 5 minutes.
- ③ Add 50μl fresh blood serum (plasma) in to correlated labelled test tube, then add 2ml pre-warmed substrate buffer, mix fastly and count time.
- ④ Transfer mixture in cuvette fastly, use spectrophotometer to measure turbidity at 420nm, record absorbance at 30 seconds as A1.
- ⑤ Pour mixture to former test tube and set in 37°C water bath for 10 minutes accurately, then transfer back to cuvette immediately, record absorbance at 10 min 30 seconds as A2.
- ⑥ Calculate difference of these two absorbances ($\Delta A=A1-A2$)

(2) Formula:

Blood serum (or plasma) LPS activity unit definition: 1L blood serum (or plasma) reacts with substrate in the reaction system at 37°C, 1μmol substrate consuming is considered as 1 LPS activity unit.

Standard tube absorbance calculation: Mix 2ml substrate buffer and 50μl physiological saline, measure turbidity at 420nm, record absorbance as As, As value equals to absorbance of standard tube concentration (454μmol/L).

$$\text{Blood serum (or plasma) LPS activity (U/L)} = \frac{A1-A2}{A_s} \times \text{Standard tube concentration (454}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Sample dilution times in reaction system} \div \text{Reaction time length (10 minutes)}$$

Note:

$$\text{Sample dilution times in reaction system} = \frac{\text{Substrate buffer volume (2ml)} + \text{Sample volume (0.050ml)}}{\text{Sample volume (0.050ml)}}$$

- ① Please cleanse cuvettes with warm distilled water before next use.
- ② Some analyzed samples (3~5%) may increase absorbance after reacting with substrate, generally they are repeated freeze-thawed or IgM increasing samples (such as rheumatoid factor).

3、Tissue LPS activity assay**(1) Operation procedure:**

- ① Use spectrophotometer, adjust zero by Tris buffer and 1cm light path glass cuvette at 420nm.
- ② Pre-warm substrate buffer at 37°C for more than 5 minutes.
- ③ Add 25μl 20% tissue homogenate supernatant in correlated labelled test tube, then add 2ml pre-warmed substrate buffer, mix fastly and count time.
- ④ Transfer mixture in cuvette fastly, use spectrophotometer to measure turbidity at 420nm, record absorbance at 30 seconds as A1.
- ⑤ Pour mixture to former test tube and set in 37°C water bath for 10 minutes accurately, then transfer back to cuvette immediately, record absorbance at 10 min 30 seconds as A2.
- ⑥ Calculate difference of these two absorbances ($\Delta A=A1-A2$)

(2) Formula:

Tissue LPS activity unit definition: 1g tissue protein reacts with substrate in the reaction system at 37°C, 1μmol substrate consuming is considered as 1 LPS activity unit.

Standard tube absorbance calculation: Mix 2ml substrate buffer and 50 μ l physiological saline, measure turbidity at 420nm, record absorbance as A_s , A_s value equals to absorbance of standard tube concentration (454 μ mol/L).

$$\text{Tissue LPS activity (U/gprot)} = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{A_s} \times \text{Standard tube concentration (454}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \text{Sample dilution times in reaction system} \div \text{Reaction time length (10 minutes)} \div \text{Protein concentration in sample homogenate (gprot/L)}$$

Note:

$$\text{Sample dilution times in reaction system} = \frac{\text{Substrate buffer volume (2ml)} + \text{Reagent 4 volume (0.025ml)} + \text{Sample volume (0.025ml)}}{\text{Sample volume (0.025ml)}}$$

4、Announcements

- (1) **20% tissue homogenate preparation:** Weigh tissue wet weight accurately, mix tissue sample (g) with physiological saline (ml) at ratio of 1:4, make homogenate in ice water bath, centrifugate at 2500rpm for 10 minutes, take supernatant for assay.
- (2) Pancreatic gland has very high LPS content, so please do pre-test in order to probe optimal sample concentration ($\Delta A \leq 0.4$)
- (3) Please cleanse cuvettes with warm distilled water before next use.
- (4) Some analyzed samples (3~5%) may increase absorbance after reacting with substrate, generally they are repeated freeze-thawed or IgM increasing samples (such as rheumatoid factor).